

CELLULOSE-ION EXCHANGE RESINS FOR PURIFICATION AND
FRACTIONATION OF PROTEINS. PART I. COBALAMIN
PROTEIN FROM HOG GASTRIC MUCOSA*

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Cobalamin protein from hog gastric mucosa has been purified by adopting cellulose-ion exchange chromatography with gradient elution technique. The protein appears to consist of at least two protein components.

The preparation and properties of a cobalamin protein (complex of a protein component plus vitamin B₁₂) from hog gastric mucosa have been reported by Stern *et al.* (*Biochim. Biophys. Acta*, 1954, 13, 144). A similar cyano-protein complex (Gregory and Holdsworth, *Nature*, 1954, 173, 830) from sow's milk and desiccated pig stomach has also been reported. By employing cellulose-ion exchange chromatography with gradient elution technique, we have recently observed that the cobalamin protein or the red protein appears to consist of at least two protein components, and it has been considerably purified by the action of cellulose-ion exchangers.

EXPERIMENTAL

The cellulose-ion exchange adsorbents were prepared according to the method of Peterson and Sober (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 78, 751). The anion exchanger, diethylaminoethyl cellulose (DEAE-), was specially suited for our work. The efficiency of this anion exchanger was tested by an actual separation of artificial mixtures of albumin with bromophenol blue and hemoglobin, and hemoglobin with cytochrome c, before it was used for the purification and fractionation of cobalamin protein. The preliminary separation, as tested by spectrophotometry, was found to be highly satisfactory. The elution technique employed was similar to that of Sober and Peterson (*ibid.*, 1956, 78, 756) for the fractionation of their serum protein by cellulose-anion exchanger.

Two cobalamin protein preparations, having different concentrations of vitamin B₁₂, were used. The following fractions were prepared by adding crystalline cyanocobalamin to hog gastric mucosa :

1. Sample A : I.F. 762, partially purified fraction (B₁₂ content 3.7 μ g. per mg.),
2. Sample C : I.F. 1732, very impure fraction (B₁₂ content 1.8 μ g. per mg.).

Method.—The chromatographic column was prepared in the following way. Alcohol-wet DEAE-cellulose (5 g.) was made a slurry with 40 c.c. of sodium phosphate buffer solution at p_H 7.7 and ionic strength 0.02 and poured into a column (13 $\times$ 1 cm) to maintain a height of 10 cm. The initial packing was done under gravity, but towards the end a nitrogen pressure of 10 lbs./sq. in. was applied to make the column more compact. About 1.70% solution (5 c.c. each) of samples A and C in sodium phosphate

* This work was carried out in the laboratory of Prof. Kurt G. Srezn, who died suddenly in London in Feb. 3, 1956, before it was completed.

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buffer solution of the same pH and ionic strength was added dropwise to the column (10×1 cm) of DEAE-cellulose. A deep red zone of about 1 cm in height was formed when the addition of the solution was complete. This was then eluted with sodium phosphate buffers of increasing ionic strengths (0.02, 0.04, 0.1 and 0.2). To obtain a convenient efflux rate of at least 10 to 12 c.c./hr., the hydrostatic head was adjusted to 60 cm with an additional long thin column. Successive fractions of 3 c.c. were then collected in a fraction collector at a flow rate of 3 c.c./15 mins. (viz., 12 c.c./1 hr.). Buffer changes were effected by completely drawing off the solutions by a syringe with a long needle and replacing it by the buffer of next higher ionic strength. Strictly speaking, this was not a gradient elution but a stepwise change. In the case of sample C, which was extremely viscous, the effluents were collected under gentle suction as the flow rate under the hydrostatic pressure was too low.

DISCUSSION

In Figs. 1 and 2, we have plotted effluent volumes of samples A and C against their optical densities at 280, 362, 410 and 550 $m\mu$ respectively. The optical density at 280 $m\mu$ is largely due to protein, at 362 and 550 $m\mu$ to cyano-cobalamin (Gregory and Holdsworth, *loc. cit.*) and at 410 $m\mu$ to hemochromogen, an impurity. It will be seen from Fig. 1 that the maximum concentration of red protein is in fraction 19. Two

FIG. 1

Sample A: Conc. 1.72% in sodium phosphate buffer; 2, 19, 23 indicate No. of tubes collected in the fraction collector showing the maximum conc. of protein and cobalamin protein.

other protein maxima occur in fractions 2 and 23. In fraction 2, however, the concentration of cyano-cobalamin is very low. This may be the reason why this

solution is practically colorless. The solution of fraction 23 is pink due to a somewhat greater concentration of cyano-cobalamin while the protein concentrations of the two fractions are practically the same in both the cases. Similarly in Fig. 2 there are three peaks at $280\text{ m}\mu$, indicating three protein components.

FIG. 2

Sample C: Conc. 1.80% in sodium phosphate buffer; 1, 9, 12 indicate No. of tubes collected in the fraction collector showing the max. conc. of protein and cobalamin protein.

For further characterisation, the isolated fractions containing the maximum concentrations of cobalamin protein were studied by spectrophotometry and electrophoresis. The complete spectrum of fraction 19 (from sample A) and fraction 1 (from sample C) are shown in Fig. 3, along with the original solutions of samples A and C from which these fractions were obtained. The spectra were determined in a Beckman quartz spectrophotometer.

It will be seen from Fig. 3 that the cobalamin protein, particularly in sample C, has been considerably purified by cellulose-ion exchanger. This is shown by their substantially reduced optical densities at $410\text{ m}\mu$ and by the clarity of the solutions. The original solutions from samples A and C were very turbid and they had to be clarified for spectrophotometric measurements by prolonged centrifugation at high speed. In contrast to the original solutions, DEAE-cellulose fractions were obtained optically clear. The considerably reduced peak at $410\text{ m}\mu$ in curve No. 4 retaining the same peaks at 362 and $550\text{ m}\mu$ with that of the original curve (No. 3) shows that substantial purification has been effected.

FIG. 3

Absorption spectra of purified fractions of cobalamin protein as compared with their original solutions.

Spectrum No. 1 : Sample A.
 Spectrum No. 2 : " fraction 19.
 Spectrum No. 3 : Sample C.
 Spectrum No. 4 : " fraction 1.

The electrophoretic mobility and separation of the cobalamin proteins was studied by Spinco Paper Electrophoresis (Block *et al.*, "A Manual of Paper Chromatography and Paper Electrophoresis", Academic Press Inc., New York, 1955). A model R type cell was used for this purpose. The coloured fractions (1 c.c.) were freeze-dried and the dry residue dissolved in 1 drop of sodium phosphate buffer at p_H 7.7 and ionic strength 0.02. Barbiturate buffer at p_H 8.6 with ionic strength 0.075, a constant current of 0.75 ma for 8 paper strips and a run of 16 hours per cell were used throughout. The original solution (1 c.c. each) from samples A and C after freeze-drying was simultaneously run for comparison. In each case duplicate strips were run. After the strips had been thoroughly dried at 100° for 1 hour, these were stained with Amido black (300 mg. Amido schwarz 10B dissolved in 45 c.c. of glacial acetic acid and 405 c.c. of absolute methanol) and destained with a mixture of 10% glacial acetic acid and 90% absolute methanol till no more dye could be washed out. The strips were then dried at room temperature. The paper strip patterns were then evaluated by an Electronic Densitometer, model 525 (Photo Volt Corporation), fitted with a graphic recorder "Servo" model 100. The patterns are shown in Fig. 4. The same patterns were obtained on repetition.

FIG. 4

Electrophoretic pattern of sample A and fractions.

ing the work after the sudden and unexpected death of Professor Kurt G. Stern in London.

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A comparison of the electrophoretic patterns from the fractions with their original solution will show that at least two cobalamin protein components exist, and they have been successfully isolated by the action of cellulose-anion exchanger.

The sample C being highly impure, the electrophoretic patterns were not very distinct. However, a colorless protein component has also been isolated from sample C. This is probably a mucoprotein which accounts for the high viscosity of this solution.

Microbiological assay of vitamin B₁₂ and clinical tests on the purified fractions could not be completed at this time but are in progress and will be reported in due course.

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